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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL JIYAD K M** bearing USN **2SU20HN001** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“IMPACT OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION STRATEGIES ON CUSTOMER RETENTION IN SBI BANK MANGALORE”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEEFA HAWWA** bearing USN **2SU20HN009** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“IMPACT OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION STRATEGIES ON CUSTOMER RETENTION IN SBI BANK MANGALORE”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMAN SAMITH bearing USN 2SU20HN010 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “IMPACT OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION STRATEGIES ON CUSTOMER RETENTION IN SBI BANK MANGALORE” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARJUN S.B bearing USN 2SU20HN013 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “THE IMPACT OF NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF AN ORGANIZATION (A CASE STUDY OF NEXUS BY PIZZA)” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHOOMIKA** bearing USN **2SU20HN017** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF AN ORGANIZATION (A CASE STUDY OF NEXUS BY PIZZA)”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWTHAM K** bearing USN **2SU20HN018** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF AN ORGANIZATION (A CASE STUDY OF NEXUS BY PIZZA)”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED AFRAZ N A bearing USN 2SU20HN024 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “THE ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED FAZIL T K bearing USN 2SU20HN026 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “THE ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANMAI SUMAN** bearing USN **2SU20HN036** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“AN EVALUATION OF MARKETING CONCEPT IN THE BANKING INDUSTRY A CASE STUDY OF UNION BANK MANGALORE”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KASIM IJAAZ bearing USN **2SU20PM001** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A STUDY ON IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SECURITY AGENTS IN PORTS**” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FAWAZ** bearing USN **2SU20PM024** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A SWTUDY OPN IMPACT OF MARINE POLLUTION IN SHIPPING OPERATIONS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENT”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHUHAIB H K** bearing USN **2SU20PM027** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A SWTUDY OPN IMPACT OF MARINE POLLUTION IN SHIPPING OPERATIONS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENT**” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHYAMNATH.T.M** bearing USN **2SU20PM041** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ONLINE COMMUNICATION AND SALES PERFORMANCE: A SURVEY OF MONEY DEPOSIT BANKS IN PORT HARCOURT”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH B NAYAK bearing USN **2SU20LS009** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A STUDY ON SIGNIFICANCE OF IT IN THE MANAGEMENT OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAINS.**” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANVITH SHETTY bearing USN 2SU20LS012 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “THE ROLE OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE SUCCESS OF MNCs” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms *ASHITH THOMAS* bearing USN *2SU20LS013* has completed his/her minor project on the topic “*THE ROLE OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE SUCCESS OF MNCs*” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms *ASHWIN JOBI* bearing USN *2SU20LS014* has completed his/her minor project on the topic “*THE ROLE OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE SUCCESS OF MNCS*” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG H DEVADIGA bearing USN **2SU20LS016** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE ROLE OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE SUCCESS OF MNCS”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CLIPTAN SALVADOR D SOUZA** bearing USN **2SU20LS017** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE ROLE OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE SUCCESS OF MNCS”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year **2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of a stylized 'K' followed by a series of loops and a long horizontal stroke.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHANRAJ bearing USN 2SU20LS018 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “THE ROLE OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE SUCCESS OF MNCS” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HITESH J S bearing USN **2SU20LS020** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE ROLE OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE SUCCESS OF MNCS”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HUSSAIN ARFAZ bearing USN 2SU20LS021 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “THE ROLE OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE SUCCESS OF MNCS” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JAMSHEED S bearing USN 2SU20LS023 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE EXISTING SUPPLY CHAIN AND LOGISTICS REGULATIONS IN THE INDIA AND CHINA” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JENITHA LOBO bearing USN 2SU20LS024 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE EXISTING SUPPLY CHAIN AND LOGISTICS REGULATIONS IN THE INDIA AND CHINA” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RAYEEF** bearing USN **2SU20LS036** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY ON PACKAGING REGULATIONS IN THE INDIA”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED HANEEF . C . M** bearing USN **2SU20LS043** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY ON PACKAGING REGULATIONS IN THE INDIA”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED RISHAD.KK bearing USN 2SU20LS045 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON FEASIBILITY OF THE WAREHOUSE MANAGEMENT FUNCTION OF FAMILY BUSINESSES IN THE INDIA” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NADEEM IFTIQAR bearing USN 2SU20LS047 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON FEASIBILITY OF THE WAREHOUSE MANAGEMENT FUNCTION OF FAMILY BUSINESSES IN THE INDIA” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUMANTH bearing USN 2SU20LS064 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ANALYZE THE ROLE OF VALUE CHAIN STRATEGY IN LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT.” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIKYATH** bearing USN **2SU20LS068** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ASSESS THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF TRANSPORT SOLUTIONS ON THE CHAIN OF RESPONSIBILITY IN THE INDIA”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NOORUL AIN ARIF bearing USN 2SU20AV040 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “THE IMPORTANT ROLE OF THE AVIATION INDUSTRY FOR THE HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM INDUSTRY” in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POOJA** bearing USN **2SU20AV041** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPORTANT ROLE OF THE AVIATION INDUSTRY FOR THE HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM INDUSTRY”** in the Second year of the BBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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